

Resource Type	Resource Name	Source	Identifier	New/Reuse	Additional Information
Dataset	LCC Luminex Data	MJFF Database	www.michaeljfox.org/data-sets	New	All samples used in this study were provided by the LCC. All raw data from this study is available in the MJFF/LCC Database.
Code	R and Python code: Luminex Analysis and GPT-4o Prompts	GitHub	https://github.com/JacksonGS-1/Team-Chen-Luminex-Project/releases/tag/v1.0.1	New	All R and Python code for analysis used in this study and GPT-4o prompts.
Software	R version 4.3.2	R Project	https://www.R-project.org/ ; RRID:SCR_001905	Reuse	Used to create figures and analyze LCC data.
Software	RStudio version 2024.04.2+764	Posit	https://posit.co/ ; RRID:SCR_000432	Reuse	R interface system.
Software	Python version 3.11.9	Python	http://www.python.org/ ; RRID:SCR_008394	Reuse	Used to create GPT-4o prompts and figures.
Software	JupyterLab version 4.1	Jupyter	https://jupyter.org/ ; RRID:SCR_018315	Reuse	Python interface system.
Software	GPT-4o	OpenAI	https://chat.openai.com/chat	Reuse	Used in literature search and comparison.
Experimental Model: Murine (C57BL/6J)	C57BL/6J Mice	Jackson Laboratory	RRID:IMSR_JAX:000664	Reuse	The control mice used in this study.
Experimental Model: Murine (LRRK2 G2019S KI)	LRRK2 G2019S Knock-In Mice	Jackson Laboratory	RRID:IMSR_JAX:030961	Reuse	The LRRK2 mice used in this study.
Protocol	ProcartaPlex™ Human Immune Monitoring Panel 65-Plex	Fisher Scientific	https://assets.thermofisher.com/TFS-Assets/LSG/manuals/MAN0024719_ProcartaPlexHumImmuneMonitoringPanel_65-Plex_UG.pdf Protocol/Catalog Number: EXP650-10065-901; MAN0024719	Reuse	Protocol used in this study to determine the level of 65 cytokines, chemokines, growth factor targets, and soluble receptors in serum and CSF samples.
Protocol	SDF-1 alpha Quantikine ELISA Kit	R&D Systems	https://resources.rndsystems.com/pdfs/datasheets/dsa00.pdf?v=20250204 Protocol/Catalog Number: MCX120	Reuse	Protocol used to quantify SDF-1 alpha in this study.
Protocol	TNF-RII Quantikine ELISA Kit	R&D Systems	https://resources.rndsystems.com/pdfs/datasheets/dta00d.pdf?v=20250204 Protocol/Catalog Number: MRT20	Reuse	Protocol used to quantify TNF-RII in this study.